

The Inclusion of RPA in the Digital Transformation

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ABSTRACT

Over time, technological evolution has had an impact on all business organizations where the need to be able to constantly innovate in all the internal processes of your company is created. Today the commercial market is very competitive and causes companies to see a deeper horizon and adopt certain methodologies and new processes such as digital transformation

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According to the consulting firm Mckinsey, due to the pandemic, it has forced many entities to advance this adoption of new technologies, including the optimization of some manual processes, which have to be automated, but before talking about these technologies, we will verify some stumbling blocks that the digital transformation has that we detail below. according to (Weaver, 2021):

- 1) The approval of the directors: This is the biggest obstacle of the 3 points because most probably the directors in their planning have invested technological tools that due to pandemic issues, these became obsolete, but according to studies at the beginning of the year 2020 (KPMG, 2020), "67% of executives in the United States expressed a great concern regarding the migration of all their businesses to the cloud, however, this quickly turned from being a concern to a necessity where as a result , 70% of managers have an affirmation that the new digital models had a great advance as a result of the pandemic".
- 2) Resistance to change in human resources: this concept is not new in the market, because the lack of communication between the project leaders and the areas involved is not very effective, resulting in an environment of uncertainty and doubts about what that is being done. This exclusion of the staff and not making them part of our project, makes many people resist change, being a great obstacle for our technological project. It is always essential to be aware that the new technologies that are being implemented will most likely be used by these users, but it should also be considered that our users are used to executing and carrying out processes that are well known and it is the change in their routine that generates some fear or discomfort.

- 3) Reduce dependence on traditional tools: for some authors, this point is the continuity of the previous one, since users know how to use the computer tools they have used for years and a new update means for them to start over from scratch. Migrating to new technological tools must mean that for the company it will bring many benefits, as well as improve the quality of life of its users.

Contrary to the previous points, the benefits obtained in the digital transformation can be indicated according to (CMC, 2020):

- 1) Faster response to changes.
- 2) Improve the customer experience.
- 3) Make better decisions.
- 4) New business opportunities.
- 5) Reduce risks.
- 6) Increases the productivity of the company.
- 7) It favors collaborative work.
- 8) Promotes innovation.
- 9) Advantage over the competition.
- 10) Decentralization of work.

The digital transformation combines three important aspects in its development, starting with an open culture, new technologies and constant processes. For the latter, they can be implemented in different ways, such as robotic process automation (RPA).

For (ToBeIt, 2022), RPA "is one of the keys to the transformation of companies since it is allowing the automation of superfluous and repetitive processes or tasks through specific rules". With this definition, various types of services can be created that lead to 24-hour care without the

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need for human intervention, of course, that the objective of RPA is not to replace human resources but rather to be able to optimize tasks carried out by users, providing the opportunity for the user to carry out other activities where they involve some type of decision.

The different RPA tools, some of them entail a certain degree of programming knowledge, but, however, there are others that are very friendly and/or are carried out through a natural language, making it possible for the same user to configure them and plan their execution, taking into account the following activities:

- 1) Security and access to the tool, through the management of credentials and the roles of each user.
- 2) Compatibility with existing applications in the company.
- 3) User interface, the application must be as friendly to new users as it is to experienced users.

In order to implement an RPA tool, it is essential to evaluate the following aspects:

- 1) Identify those repetitive tasks that consume many hours of work.
- 2) Design and parameterization of the optimized workflow.
- 3) Planning the implementation of the RPA tool together with constant monitoring of its execution.

The benefits of implementing an RPA are:

- 1) Realization and execution of tasks 24*7 without the need for human intervention.
- 2) Greater efficiency between 50% and 90% of current processes.
- 3) Time savings, since the robot is much faster than human action.
- 4) Because it has no human intervention, it can be said that the RPA has a margin of error of 0%.
- 5) An RPA can be implemented without the intervention of a company IT team.

According to the magic square of Garther 2021 "estimates that 85% of companies with revenues greater than 1,000 million dollars will have deployed RPA by the end of the year 2022, a percentage that at the end of 2018 was 60%". Another very important fact is that a study by (Hidalgo, 2022) indicates that "in 2021, the business volume linked to this technology has been approximately \$2B and an exponential growth of the RPA market is expected until it reaches a volume of 13.4B\$ in the year 2030". This information tells us that many companies are investing in RPA due to the benefits that they imply.

In a report generated in (flobotics-io, 2022) it indicates that "the use of RPA in industries, 38% is insurance companies, 36% is retail and hospitality, 30% is energy companies and utilities, with the same percentage is in health care companies, 24% in banking and financial entities and finally

with 22% in pharmaceutical industries and others". The types of companies not mentioned, have a low percentage of participation, but little by little they are increasing to adapt to this type of technology.

In a survey issued by Deloitte, 92% indicated that RPA met or exceeded their expectations while 90% indicated that they had improved quality/accuracy, 86% improved productivity, and 59% indicated that they had a reduction in cost. costs. Another important piece of information is that 78% of companies that have implemented RPA expect to significantly increase their investment in RPA over the next three years. There is another very important statistic where it finds that 63% of companies plan to engage with an RPA implementation partner, while 19% plan to use RPA vendors for support and 15% will handle RPA internally.

Finally, I can conclude that the inclusion of RPA in the digital transformation is very important for the competitive advantages that a company can have, since with it they manage to optimize their resources and generate great business opportunities, without forgetting the new services that a company can provide to its customers to improve the experience and satisfaction of this.

REFERENCES

1. CMC. (September 28, 2020). CMC. Retrieved from <https://www.grupocmc.es/blog/10ventajas-transformacion-digital/>
2. flobotics-io. (2022). flobotics-io. Retrieved from
3. https://flobotics-io.translate.google.com/blog/rpa-statistics/?_x_tr_sl=en&_x_tr_tl=es&_x_tr_hl=es&_x_tr_pto=sc
4. Hidalgo, A. (June 21, 2022). Alten. Retrieved from <https://www.alten.es/estrategias-ytendencias-en-el-mercado-rpa-para-2022/>
5. KPMG. (September 2020). KPMG. Retrieved from <https://home.kpmg/us/en/home/insights/2020/09/digital-acceleration.html>
6. ToBeIt. (2022). ToBeIt. Retrieved from <https://tobeit.es/rpa-eje-transformacion-digital/>
7. Weaver, B. (October 12, 2021). Wrike. Retrieved from <https://www.wrike.com/es/blog/five-challenges-of-the-digital-transformation-and-how-to-face-them/>